

Mastering Global Expansion

Developed by: TOPSIM GmbH

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Keywords

Accounting, Business, Competition, Cooperation, Financial Management, International Management, Marketing, Production Management, Project Management, Risk Management, Strategic Decision-making, Supply Chain Management

Figure 1. Graphic from *Mastering Global Expansion*. Rights owned by TOPSIM GmbH; used here for educational review.

Introduction

Mastering Global Expansion (see Figure 1) is a strategic business simulation focused on internationalization. Participants assume executive management of a manufacturing firm and develop expansion strategies for the global market. The objective is to ensure long-term business success by making informed decisions across market entry, marketing, production, and finance.

The simulation is aimed at executives, students, and decision-makers who deal with global markets and corporate strategies. As a serious game, it combines practical learning with game-based simulation, promoting strategic thinking and entrepreneurial competencies.

The round-based structure challenges teams to conduct market analyses, plan investments, and outperform competing teams. The simulation is based on the established TOPSIM business simulation concept, which has been used for over 40 years. Version 7.2 of *Mastering Global Expansion* was first released in the TOPSIM Cloud in 2015 and has been continuously developed since then.

Facts

Release date:	Initial cloud release: Version 7.2 (February 2015). Current version: 7.4.2 (April 2022)
Developer:	TOPSIM GmbH
Game type:	Digital hybrid (at least one player per team requires internet access)
Number of players:	Optimum: 9–25 (3–5 groups of 3–5 persons each) per market. Multiple markets are possible. The number of players is infinitely scalable.
Format:	Asynchronous, Hybrid
Time frame:	Approx. 16–32 hours, depending on how many of the eight periods are played, the implementation format, and whether evaluations and additional tasks are integrated. Time requirements depend on the intended learning goals.
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Device: Tablet, PC, or laptop (minimum 720p). Browsers: Chrome, Firefox, or Safari. Internet connection required.
Material:	Participants receive an introduction, a participant handbook, business news, and seminar materials. Facilitators receive a facilitator handbook. Short description: https://www.topsim.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Mastering_Global_Expansion_Flyer.pdf Blog article: https://www.topsim.com/blog/den-weltmarkt-erobern-mit-mastering-global-expansion/
Price:	TOPSIM simulations are fee-based. Pricing depends on the simulation, number of participants, and usage model. Direct inquiry with TOPSIM is recommended.

Resonance & Criticism

Mastering Global Expansion is an advanced simulation focused on a company's internationalization. It is used in advanced business programs as well as executive and corporate training.

The competition-oriented simulation models the challenges of global expansion and strengthens strategic thinking in an international context. While exact user numbers are not publicly available, the simulation is used in educational institutions and companies such as trainM GmbH to foster cross-functional collaboration and entrepreneurial understanding (TOPSIM GmbH, 2024).

No specific evaluations or awards are currently known. However, TOPSIM simulations are generally praised for their practical approach to teaching complex business topics.

Game Principle & Process

In Mastering Global Expansion, participants lead a company that expands from its home region into six international markets (Europe, North America, South America, Central Asia, Asia-Pacific, and Africa).

The round-based simulation spans up to eight periods (fiscal years). In each period, teams make decisions regarding market entry, marketing, research and development, production, procurement, finance, sales, and human resources. Later in the simulation, global expansion and financing decisions are added, resulting in up to 93 decisions per round. A typical session takes 16 to 32 hours and is usually divided into two or three seminar blocks.

The objective is to operate profitably in all regions in which the company expands. Automated evaluations and market reports generated after each round provide immediate feedback on earnings, market shares, and risks, allowing continuous strategy adjustments.

Teams consist of three to five participants. Four to six teams compete simultaneously. Collaborative decision-making enhances communication, while benchmarking intensifies competition.

The facilitator training includes a one-day (8-hour) webinar and approximately four hours of self-study with a manual and demo scenario. This ensures instructors become familiar with the interface, analysis tools, and didactic applications.

The simulation is grounded in international and strategic management theory and realistically models corporate missions, market barriers, and market entry strategies.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Mastering Global Expansion introduces participants to the challenges of internationalization and equips them with the skills to make strategic decisions in a global context. The simulation encourages strategic thinking by requiring participants to develop and implement well-founded corporate strategies for international market expansion.

Participants analyze new markets, evaluate opportunities and risks, and develop market entry strategies and address potential market barriers.

In addition to professional competencies, the simulation strengthens social and communication skills. Teams discuss strategic options, make decisions together under uncertainty and time pressure, and implement those decisions across business areas such as marketing, production, procurement, and finance. Immediate feedback across periods promotes problem-solving and collaboration.

The round-based structure simulates real market conditions and competitive dynamics. Immediate feedback and evaluations deepen understanding of economic relationships.

Instructors introduce the mechanics and lead reflection phases. Depending on group size, additional support may be beneficial.

The simulation encompasses multiple business domains and prepares participants for real challenges in international management. Participants develop a holistic understanding of business processes and gain practical experience applying strategic and analytical skills.

Effectiveness

No specific empirical studies on the effectiveness of Mastering Global Expansion currently exist. However, general serious-game research demonstrates positive effects on learning outcomes. For example, Eckardt et al. (2017) found that participation in a serious game improved learning outcomes and increased motivation, enjoyment, and satisfaction compared to traditional lectures.

Regarding long-term learning effects, studies indicate that serious games can enhance knowledge retention. A meta-analysis found that digital games improve learning and increase learner motivation (Knogler et al., 2017).

Research on immersion and flow suggests that well-designed serious games can induce a flow state—an immersive balance between challenge and ability—which enhances engagement and learning (Hoblitz, 2015).

Overall, general findings on serious games suggest positive effects on motivation, learning outcomes, and immersion.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Mastering Global Expansion contains no sensitive or problematic content such as violence, drug abuse, or discriminatory depictions. It focuses on economic decisions and uses neutral, realistic scenarios.

Ethical considerations of globalization—such as social responsibility and sustainable growth—are incorporated, but the simulation presumes foundational business knowledge, which may pose accessibility challenges for beginners.

There are no physical or technical barriers beyond standard digital access requirements. However, individuals with visual or motor impairments may require additional support.

Reviewer(s): Hannes Hamester

Sources

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